

GEARTIVITY AND LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract: This article presents scientific opinions on methodological aspects of teaching topics, teaching methods and stages in the process of language learning and mastery. The experiences and methods of Uzbek and foreign specialists in teaching a foreign language are studied and analyzed in detail.

Keywords: Foreign language, methodology, style, language learning, language acquisition, methodological aspect.

The processes of world globalization, the unprecedented expansion of intercultural relations between states, nations and cultures have made the issue of full-fledged dialogue between representatives of different peoples urgent. Full dialogue, first of all, includes language relations. Knowledge of a foreign language increases the level of knowledge, broadens the worldview, and contributes to a more tolerant perception of the world around us. Language plays an important role in the mutual development and exchange of experience between countries. Therefore, in recent years, the need to learn a language has been increasing day by day. Language is the main tool in conducting the most important diplomatic relations between two countries. It is known from history that in order to establish strong ties between neighboring or distant countries, the first task assigned to ambassadors was, of course, to learn the language of that country and establish strong ties through strong diplomatic efforts. Fundamental reforms in the global education system are putting forward the problems of creating the necessary conditions for students to master foreign languages, to express themselves in all fields with knowledge of a foreign language, and to develop their oral and written speech in a foreign language.

The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is invaluable. The use of technological tools is useful in every aspect of learning the Korean language (reading, writing, listening comprehension and speaking). For example, for listening comprehension, this process cannot be carried out without a computer, player, CD discs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. In this, the student is required to pay attention to the speaker's

pronunciation, compliance with grammatical rules, vocabulary and its meanings at the same time. When using modern technologies in the educational process, it is also an important factor that students know and can use information and communication technologies well.

The methodology of teaching subjects in foreign language teaching has a history of more than 200 years as a science. During this period, it can be observed that different attitudes have been expressed towards the methodology of teaching a foreign language. One of such views belongs to academician L.V. Shcherba.

In his opinion, the methodology of teaching any subject, despite being a science, is not a theoretical science. It solves practical problems. In particular, the methodology of teaching a foreign language is not based only on psychological evidence, but is based on general and special linguistic research. If linguistics deals with the laws of the origin and movement of language phenomena, then the methodology answers the question of what needs to be done to use the necessary language phenomenon in practice, based on these laws. The most valuable books on methodology were also written by linguists.

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